

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

Project Acronym:	Ageing@Work
Project Full Name:	Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability
Grant Agreement:	No 826299
Project Duration:	3 ½ years (starting 1 January 2019)

Deliverable 5.2

Personalized reward-based worker motivation system

Work Package:	WP5: The Ageing@Work Virtual Coach
Task:	T5.3 Personalized reward-based worker motivation system
Lead Beneficiary:	SAMSUNG
Due Date:	M28
Submission Date:	M36
Deliverable Status:	Final
Deliverable Style:	Other
Dissemination Level:	PU
File Name:	D5.2 Personalized reward-based worker motivation system.pdf

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 826299

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Version History

Version	Date	Modifications
0.1	01/04/2021	First draft
0.2	12/10/2021	Second draft
0.3	18/11/2021	Contributions provided by partners
0.4	15/11/2021	First full version of the deliverable
0.5	05/01/2022	Final version

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to present the results of the **Personalized Reward-Based Worker Motivation Framework** included in the Ageing@Work platform. In order to help the workers maintain balance between **professional life** - in terms of their workability and productivity - and **private life** – in terms active, healthy ageing and quality of life, a literature review was conducted on Motivation and Reward concepts for employees, looking at both **Intrinsic** and **Extrinsic elements** that characterize them. In that respect, we have been focusing on the design, the development and implementation of two main categories of services: *i) Rewards System* for codifying achievements into recognition and *ii) Fitness&Wellbeing Planner* for providing wellbeing recommendations for promoting a healthier lifestyle and inducing professionals to adopt healthy habits.

With respect to the first, the overall goal has been focusing on the implementation of personalized and integrated **reward component** on the basis of **psychology-oriented, active** and **healthy ageing**, workability and occupational health studies, building upon the preparatory work performed in T1.1 and T1.2, providing a symbolic recognition of achievements and allowing the worker to be redeemed according to the company policy.

With respect to the second, the overall goal has been focusing on the implementation of personalized **Fitness&Wellness Planner component** to support the **monitoring**, the **analysis** and **health recommendations** in corresponding to anthropometric measurements including, Waist circumference, BMI (weighting scale), Body fat (weighting scale), Physical activity, Step Count - Total number of steps, Distance - Distance in meters during the activity -, Calorie Burnt - Burned calories in kilocalories during the activity, and Sleep & Sleep patterns. All measured by smartwatch.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
BMI	Body Mass Index
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
HQoL	Health and Quality of Life
JP	Job Performance
MDD	Major Depressive Disorder
ML	Machine Learning
USD	United States Dollar
WHtR	Waist To Height Ratio
WI	Workability Index
WP	Work Package
wVUM	Worker Virtual User Model

Table 1: Definitions

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

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1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

We will elaborate more on SoA and the positioning of the system being developed in T5.3, both in respect of which exact best practices and approaches have been adopted by the relevant theory herein, as well as what is the relation and advances of the proposed system, compared to relevant systems that have been proposed in the literature or exist, either as e.g. open source applications, or as systems that are used in companies, including the project's end user partners

Further investigate the current motivation approaches that are being followed in the project end user partners; these motivation approaches should also be documented in the user requirements analysis deliverable (D2.1).

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is as follows: In Section 2, the requirements of the pilots which are based on their different context are presented. Section 3 continues with the presentation of the whole personalized rewarding system from the conceptualization to the actual implementation. In subsection 3.1.1 a presentation of the literature review regarding rewarding systems for industrial premises is presented. Subsection 3.1.2 includes the integration of health and fitness applications while subsection 3.1.3 presents the conceptualization of the personalized rewarding strategy which is followed in the Ageing@Work framework. The 3.1.4 subsection presents the results and outcomes of the application of the personalized system in terms of action based rules. The deliverable concludes with section 4, which presents an overview of the activities taken so far and the future work which will be presented in D7.3.

2. The Context and Requirements

2.1 ANEFA & Siemens

In order to create the appropriate rewarding strategy, it is essential to define the aim of the rewarding system. Rewarding system is responsible for motivating the user to perform an activity which is not familiar to them or for which they are not aware of the benefits or they have difficulty to perform. The main target of the rewarding system is to keep the balance between the Workability index(WI), Job Performance (JP) and the Health and Quality of Life index (HQoL). Based on the data collection presented in D3.1, there are specific factors that constitute these two indexes and are highly correlated. The goal of the personalized rewarding system is to encourage workers to perform actions that either enhance or prevent the increase of their values according to whether the factor is positively or negatively correlated. In order to achieve an equilibrium of WI, JB and HQoL in a worker's daily routine we need a mechanism that monitors the values of the factors and motivates the worker to act appropriately in order to maintain it. Thus, according to personal habits and behavior captured through mobile apps and self-reporting, both WI, JB and HQoL are formed and the rewarding system is responsible for keeping the equilibrium. As we mentioned in 2.1, there are differences in the factors that form these indexes for ANEFA and Siemens, fact which makes sense since their context and requirements are different. Thus, rewarding rules are implemented for all the correlated factors based on D3.1 but they are applied based on the needs of each pilot site.

In general, for the Ageing@Work project, **the workability index (WI), job performance (JB) and health-quality of life (HQoL) for ANEFA** include the following factors:

WI -> Stress, NegativeFeelings, SleepSatisfaction, Concentration, selfEfficacy, satisfactionWithPersonalRelationships

JP -> SleepSatisfaction, Concentration, selfEfficacy, satisfactionPersonalRelationship, motivationAndInvolvementInWork, PhysicalExertionAtWork, CognitiveDemands, ConflictsAndQuarrels

HQoL -> Stress, SleepSatisfaction, Concentration, selfEfficacy, satisfactionPersonalRelationship, socialPrivateLife, vibrationsHandTools

On the other hand, **the workability index (WI), job performance (JB) and health-quality of life (HQoL) for Siemens** include the following factors with initial weights found from correlations:

WI -> painfulPositions, highTemperature, breathingInVapours, nutrition, physicFatigue, satisfactionWithSupportFriends, socialSupportSupervisor

JP -> painfulPositions, physicalFatigue, satisfactionSupportFromFriends, socialSupportFromColleagues

HQoL -> workingHours, tempo(timePressure), highTemperature, breathingInVapours, physicFatigue, satisfactionSupportFriends, jobSatisfaction, satisfactionAccessToHealthServices, workLifeConflict, variationOfWork, repetitiveHandsArmMovement, OSHRiskAwareness, socialSupportSupervisor

In case of a physical fatigue which is negatively correlated with WI regarding the Siemens premises, the Ageing@Work system suggests to adjust the employees shift with a more convenient one or to take a day off, if available, in order to get some rest. Positive rewards are given once the adjustment is performed based on the trade-off between assigned tasks completion and personal skills and capacity (see wVUM model). The rewarding system in order to be personalized, needs to be based on the beliefs and values of each worker separately, thus based on VUM questionnaire, positive rewards are adapted based on the personal life aspects and the worker's prioritization. The three main aspects of the rewarding system is to promote personal's health and well-being by:

- Increasing physical activities;
- Adapting an adequate and proper rest behavior;
- Increasing of activities involving a strong social dimension

For these three main aspects, wVUM keeps the preferences of each worker regarding the performance of these aspects, so that rewarding is implemented according to these preferences for a more personalized approach.

3. The Reward Engine

3.1 State of the Art

Over the past years, it has been claimed that personalized rewards make better benefits and there are specific reasons for which this happens [1]. Until recently, rewarding the employees under certain rules may have been enough since there was no way of personalizing somehow the process. However, the large volume of available data along with the technology evolution offer opportunities towards personalization in rewarding systems. Personalization technology such as digital platforms are evolving continuously, thus along with the available information, tailored rewards to meet employees expectations has become a more feasible idea. This is due to the fact that successful use of such kind of platforms is often linked to positive organizational culture, which reflects the behaviours that describe the unique social and psychological environment of an organization. In the study [2] six guidelines for culture change are proposed since working environments has started to be diverse. Because of the technological advancements which are based on cloud systems and remote desktops, working environments are more flexible. Thus, encouraging worker motivation and worker training to new working habits and personal life activities, are important steps towards a balanced and healthy life.

Balance between the two main dimensions of a person's life, professional and personal life, can be challenging, however, it is essential. Often enough, work takes over a person's daily time since the common desire is to succeed professionally and sometimes at any costs. Therefore, a person's well-being is set aside, fact that harms either physical or mental health quite frequently. Thus, being able to create a harmony between the factors that affect personal life and professional life, may benefit not only the physical, emotional and mental well-being but also the professional career. In terms of Ageing@Work, the consortium had to deal with the ageing of the workers and the adjustment of human resources in such ways to keep their competitiveness and their well-being. A major question that has risen in this case, was whether the age of the worker defines the way they assess work-life balance [3]. Results indicate that workers who represent older age groups are more likely to refer to the importance of maintaining a work-life balance. Thus, managers and employers have to be inspired by this opportunity and start creating workspaces with conditions that encourage the senior worker to participate and not feel outsiders once they reach a specific age. Usually, adaptations in working environments refer to additions of new technologies thus an attractive way of introducing them is through personalized rewarding also known as gamification.

Gamification – the use of game design elements in non-game contexts – has seen rapid adoption in recent years, and since there are challenges and open research questions in the design of a successful gamification strategy, various social and psychological theories have been investigated as well in an attempt to enhance the mechanics [4-6]. The gamification concept in industrial work environments is emerging and it can be applied to different cases such as for making the execution of repetitive tasks more interesting and joyful, motivating workers to perform recommended tasks that often neglect, motivating

workers to share knowledge, exchange ideas and view training content [7], motivating workers to try new technology in their working environment and motivate workers to change behavior for improving their well-being. We have focused on the last two cases in this project, in an attempt to understand the factors that constitute professional life and the factors that constitute personal life and should change to conclude in better balance for each worker separately.

The developed suite of age-friendly and personalized tools for the productivity and workability of the elder workers is based on the wVUM which is described in deliverable D3.2. User acceptance evaluation events gather input from actual system users to determine where potential problems may exist in new software or major upgrade [8]. User acceptance evaluations of the newly introduced technologies that are designed to be used by workers in working environments are essential because the main target of their use is to enhance workability. A software application should be designed carefully since otherwise it can discourage users from using it. Additionally, the solution of personalized rewarding is intended to be used in two pilot sites thus two different work environments, so it must satisfy both of them by meeting the objectives and needs of all types of users. The feedback acquired from such evaluations is valuable as it can verify the success or failure of the rewarding strategy applied at pilot sites. Moreover, it can be used for adapting the provided rewards or change the rewarding strategy to fit better to the organization's specific needs.

In this project, we present a holistic approach in terms of encouraging with rewards specific behaviors which benefit the elder workers and motivate them to maintain professional and personal life. In order to achieve the holistic approach, internet-linked devices have contributed a lot by offering a plethora of monitoring possibilities from health and well-being data [9]. Mobile applications and data coming from smartphones, smartwatches and other smart devices create the environment from which the workers have a self-monitoring tool and the personalized rewarding system receives all the necessary information to form appropriate rules. Apart from smart devices, data for well-being is also collected by self-reports and answers given to validated questionnaires. Thus, with the combination of these sources, we managed to unobtrusively have a detailed digital representation of the workers which helps to diagnose and intervene if necessary for prevention or treatment.

In cases where elder workers are concerned, it is important to motivate them to use technology for monitoring their well-being. For example, Canzian et al. [31], through the usage of location-related data, have managed to find significant correlations between the smartphone-driven features and the disease state of patients with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD). Wang et al. [11], reported significant predictors for personality traits, with data derived from mobile application which recorded activity data, conversations (number and duration), smartphone usage and location. A different source of data, derived from smart-screen keyboard typing dynamics seems to be able to correlate mental disorder scores for MDD [12], Bipolar Disorder [13] and Parkinson's disease [14], associating psychomotor retardation with keyboard typing. Additionally, the employment of multimodal sensing capabilities, often can increase the accuracy of predictive or diagnostic outcomes [36]. Chen et al. [16], combining different sources of information from location, activity, typing, surveys and phone usage features managed to accurately distinguish the patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment or Alzheimer's Disease from healthy controls.

The current implementation of the Ageing@Work application supports the data collection of activity information from:

- Smartphone
- wearable devices
- third party applications
- keystroke typing data
- location information
- medical data
- environmental IoT
- personality self-reports
- mood self-reports

All of these data have been reported, each individually but also in combinations, to be suitable for monitoring and classification purposes among healthy controls and elder workers with possible signs of mental issues. Bearing in mind that depression is considered the most common mental illness with an estimated share of 25–30% [17], the Ageing@Work infrastructure motivates elder workers to be active and balanced between the activities they perform at work and during their leisure time. Moreover, managers of the two pilot sites are motivated to keep an eye over their elder employees and adjust the shifts or even the type of work to accommodate the needs of the ageing workforce. Furthermore, as the Virtual Coach is already using the extroversion score as a mean for appearance modifications, we have used personality dimensions as additional personalization factors for rewarding [18].

Personalized rewarding has been applied to a large number of studies [23] during the recent years presenting gamification applications in a wide range of contexts, such as education [24-26], work [27-30], and innovation [31], among others. Two fields that make a wide use of gamification techniques are education and knowledge sharing since they seek to strengthen motivation and engagement [32]. In terms of the project, motivation and engagement are also necessary in order to keep elder worker active and satisfied with their daily life. Motivation is needed for both maintaining balance in professional and personal life and utilizing new technological tools offered to facilitate execution of tasks.

Personalized rewarding is also achieved through serious games which according to a broader definition, are any piece of software that merges a non-entertaining purpose with a video game structure [33]. A literature review has been done in [34] where the authors present a list of serious games which are used in the business environment. Results and evaluation indicate that serious games have positive impacts in training, decision-support, and consumer outreach. For sure there are also challenges and pitfalls when applying gamification principles within a business context thus, the business model of the organizations in both pilots has been studied before designing the gamification strategy. The interaction and linking between the development of a serious game and the game's business model is explored in study [35]. As done by the authors of [36], we have examined the use of personalized rewarding in the IoT-enabled mobile application which provides personalized recommendation tips to workers for adopting activities that encourage the balance and well-being in a worker's life. Questionnaires results revealed that the

application has potential to be used if includes at least three game design elements: progression, levels and points. The incorporation of gamification mechanics for improving participation in knowledge management processes has been investigated in paper [37], where results showed some improvement in aspects like participation, contribution and knowledge refinement in the process of software development. In [38] the authors study the increasing adoption of enterprise social networking platforms by organizations and present survey results from business professionals to examine current views of these platforms.

Furthermore, user evaluation of the personalized rewarding system is implemented as well since it is commonly used in the literature for exploring the impact of new methods and software tools on users. For example, the authors of [39] investigate how user interface design affects older people's intention and attitude related to using social networking sites. To this end, they evaluate a social application specifically designed for the elderly. In Ageing@Work system, we evaluate if there is difference in intention to follow Virtual Agent's recommendations, use the tools introduced to the elder workers and in general use more the proposed solution after the application of the personalized rewarding system. User acceptance evaluations of gamified processes utilized in software platforms are also found in the literature. In study [40], the acceptance of gamified work processes in the automotive industry is evaluated and results reveal that the general acceptance is higher when personalized rewarding rules are adapted to the requirements of the business model. On the other hand, in paper [41] the authors study the effect of rewards like points and leaderboards within an online competition supporting new ideas. User evaluation is received through participants' feedback through questionnaires and results showed that if rewards are applied inadequately they are not efficient and motivating.

Thus, efforts have been made for adaptive personalized reward systems which enhances traditional rewarding approaches with the use of user-centered, personalized incentive mechanisms. A list of the latest current studies and experiments in adaptive rewarding systems can be found in [42]. A design framework for systematic development of adaptive rewarding applications is proposed in [43]. The evaluation of the adaptive rewarding system is performed through an online knowledge exchange platform and it indicates positive results regarding user acceptance while it increased the system's usage. The authors in [44] examined the adaptive personalized rewarding system for learning environments where a linear model between player types and rewarding features has been presented. This system selects rewarding features by taking into consideration the player type of the user, therefore not all users are rewarded by same rewarding features. This creates a variation and results showed that learners with adapted rewarding features spend more time in the learning environment because motivation is stronger.

On the nature on Motivation now, it is possible to examine it as a type of Behavior (and Motivated Outcomes) any direct observable and measurable action made by a living person in terms of effort, performance, productivity, affective experience, satisfaction, engagement and performances. Moreover, as a type of Process (Process of motivation), any individual thoughts and feeling that are personal and usually cannot be directly observable and measurable [45, 46] is also called motivation. For example: "I like Machine Learning and Semantic [Mental Process/Process of motivation], so I develop and implement

algorithms that combine ML and Semantic [Behaviour]”. There are many aspects that encourage the performance of a specific behaviors or the modification of specific behaviors.

The main features of Behavioral Modification in relation to Health Apps that we can find in the literature are:

- smoking cessation [47]
- alcohol reduction, [48]
- physical activity [49]
- for specific medical conditions [50]
- mental health [51]

In addition, McKay, Wright and Shill 2019 in [52] rated the effectiveness aspects of the apps to enable changing behaviors:

- Practice and rehearsal refers to the performance of trials of the targeted behavior one or more times in a context or at a time when the performance may not be necessary, in order to increase habit and skill, e.g. provide instruction to user to practice creating and using medication schedules.
- Self-monitoring refers to establish a method for the person to monitor and record their behavior(s) as part of a behavior modification strategy, e.g. a dialog box that allows users to record whether they performed or skipped the proposed action.
- Customizing attributes refers to provide the choice to the user to tailor-make several features in the app.
- Setting Goal refers to the provision of tangible end points of the use of the app where the goals can be customized, including nutrition [53] and physical activity [54].

On the nature of Reward. It has been identified by several studies as an important feature that has potentials to bring behavioral modification (e.g. Middelweerd et al 2014 [55]; McKay, Wright and Shill 2019 [52]). The most important categories of rewards are the followings:

- **Material Reward:** provide money, vouchers or other valued objects if and only if there has been effort and/or progress made towards performing the behavior
- **Token economy:** reinforce the wanted behavior by offering tokens that can be exchanged for valued commodities
- **Social Reward:** a verbal or non-verbal reward if and only if there has been effort and/or progress in performing the behavior. Examples of social rewards: praise, compliments, words of appreciation, affection, attention
- **Self-Reward:** encourage to provide self with material (e.g., new clothes) or other valued objects if and only if they have adhered to a proposed behavior

On the dominant workplace Motivation theories and how they approach Reward. In the literature, we could identify two groups of theories, addressing the external and extrinsic rewards, as reported below, and the Self-Determination Theory as the predominant one for connecting Motivation with Reward:

- **Group A:** theories which advocate the use of *external rewards* to enhance overall motivation
 - Behaviorist Theory
 - Needs based Theory
 - Goal-setting Theory
 - Expectancy Theory
- **Group B:** theories which advocate the use of *extrinsic rewards* 'undermine' intrinsic motivation
 - Over-justification Theory
 - Crowding-out Theory
 - Reward, intrinsic motivation and creativity
 - Reward salience
- **Self-Determination Theory** which is an empirically derived theory about motivation and personality in contexts that require the differentiation of the autonomous and controlled motivation [56].

Thus, the success of personalized rewarding system is a matter of understanding the difficulties that the target group members face and motivate them to use the suggested project's solution by rewarding them appropriately. Based on the large amount of available data coming from mobile apps and self-reporting questionnaires, adaptation and personalization of rules for rewarding has become achievable.

3.1.1 Overview: mHealth Apps

According to Europe mHealth Market Research Report, 2020-2025 (<https://www.marketdataforecast.com/market-reports/europe-mobile-health-market>), the overall size of the mHealth¹ market in Europe is valued at USD 6.55 Billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 28.61 Billion by 2025. On the other hand, the global mHealth market is expected to reach USD 111.8 billion by 2025, growing at a CAGR of 44.2% [57]. It has been found that mHealth applications using mobile and other devices are an effective way to provide user-friendly healthcare services and recommendations. These apps educate users and create awareness for general healthy lifestyle and help early detection of a suite of diseases.

There are a number of patient or user-centered apps that provide a wide array of functions, such as, managing chronic disease, lifestyle management, meditation, nutrition, period-tracking, sleep

¹ World Health Organization defines mHealth as the "use of mobile and wireless technologies to support the achievement of health objectives."

monitoring, smoking cessation and even self-diagnosis. A big chunk of these apps belong to the exercise and weight loss category [58]. These allow users to record daily intake of food and drink along with the measurements of body weight and objectively-measured physical activity (obtained from a Bluetooth-enabled accelerometer) [59, 60]. Kamel Boulos and Yang conducted an elaborate survey of location-based (outdoor) gaming apps that allow users to share information through online social networks and gamification principles on GPS-enabled smartphones. These apps act as a ‘game map’ or playground where players can even discover and learn about new places while burning calories and keeping fit [60]. Based on a report by Deep Knowledge Ventures, currently, there are very few projects with AI incorporated into Health mobile apps, as well as apps that employ advanced data science and AI-empowered big data analysis to create personalized AI recommendation systems that will become the key features in the coming years [57].

Figure 1 provides a quick overview of various Healthapps available in the market.

Figure 1: Health Tech Mobile Apps: Landscape Overview (www.analytics.dkv.global)

3.1.2 Health/Fitness Apps

According to Deep Knowledge Ventures’ report [57], “Health and fitness apps usage shows an exponential growth of more 330% in the last few years according to research by Flurry Analytics. Advances in artificial intelligence currently allows apps to understand individual cases and respond to questions from users with relevant follow up queries. Fitness and nutrition apps follow caloric intake and activity.

Integration with wearables expand their capabilities dramatically. Health and fitness apps show very high retention rates. According to the research by Flurry Analytics, over 75% of active users open their health and fitness app at least two times a week, and more than 25% of users access their fitness apps more than 10 times a week. The high frequency of usage drives up engagement, which, for app developers, presents an attractive opportunity to increase monetization. What’s more, health and fitness app users are loyal, with 96% of them sticking to only one app. But that also means that new incumbents will find it difficult to acquire users”. According to this report, the three core trends and technology spheres will have an increasing impact on the mHealth mobile industry, namely:

- Personalized Preventive Medicine with focus on Longevity
- Data Science & Artificial Intelligence
- Blockchain and other next generation IT-technologies

In developed countries, people are, in average, becoming more physically active. However, the body fatness remains an open issue. Several indexes (such as Body Mass Index (BMI) and Waist-To-Height Ratio (WHtR) that characterize body fatness requires a lot of knowledge, maintenance, rescheduling, and so on, about how to get them right. This poses an opportunity risk, especially after six months of weight loss, in not being able get people to fill the gap between current lifestyle habits and those habits that hope to change, especially during period such as COVID-19. To tackle this issues, some of the gadgets and apps that are already available in the market are listed in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Popular Health Apps in the current Market

Application	Website
Fitbit	https://www.fitbit.com/uk/app
Samsung Health	https://www.samsung.com/global/galaxy/apps/samsung-health/
MyChart	https://mychart.clevelandclinic.org/
Lark	https://www.web.lark.com/
Garmin Vivoactive	https://buy.garmin.com/en-US/US/p/150767
Flo	https://flo.health/
Apple Watch	https://www.apple.com/uk/healthcare/apple-watch/
iCareHealthMonitor	http://www.icarefit.com/
Health 365	https://www.healthhub.sg/apps/25/healthy365
Calorie Counter	https://www.myfitnesspal.com/
Babylon	www.babylonhealth.com
Lose it!	http://www.loseit.com/
Noom Coach	https://www.noom.com/
Gyrosco	https://gyrosco.pe/

More on the Motivation & Rewards System Application Review.

Virgin Pulse

(https://www.virginpulse.com/engb/?tr_cp_id=zkpZ&tr_a_id=jw6D&tr_pn_id=kx5B&tr_v_idx=4v&tr_redirect=1), users are Rewarded Health Miles for calories tracked, exercise tracked, and special programs completed. Users could then trade in their reward miles for gift cards.

Higi (<https://higi.com/>): it rewards users for a multitude of health-orientated tasks. Higi syncs with your fitness tracker apps and rewards you points for steps taken and exercise completed. Higi’s rewards are not the best. There is not an option to redeem your points for cash or gift cards. Instead, you can redeem your points for coupons or free health products. One can redeem points for a 25% off coupon for Garmin products.

AchieveMint (<http://www.achievemint.com/>): it is a platform that aggregates data from select fitness, health and social networking apps you're already using and rewards you with points for healthy behaviour; integrates with platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Foursquare, Meetup, RunKeeper, MapMyFitness and Fitbit; Go for a run, tweet something "healthy," check-in to a health food store or do anything vaguely related to health that's tracked and you'll be rewarded with points on the free service. Once you achieve enough points, you can convert them into merchandise or cash. One thousand points is equivalent to \$1.

Walgreens Balance Rewards as a way to earn points on purchases and healthy activity, it syncs with popular fitness trackers and apps and supports a number of features as showed below.

Test blood pressure 20 points/daily log ⁸		
Monitor blood glucose 20 points/daily log ⁹		
Quit tobacco with NRT 20 points/daily log ¹⁰		

DietBet (<https://www.dietbet.com/>): it allows anyone to gamble legally and get healthy at the same time to win the DietBet round, one will have to lose Kilos; Winners usually get one-and-a-half to two times their bet.

The aforementioned digital applications have embedded system of personalized rewards to motivate users maintain a healthy and active balance of their life by gathering information from various smart devices and mobile apps.

3.1.3 Concept, Design and Architecture

The personalized rewarding system is a web-platform whose architecture is implemented in a fully customizable environment where the administrator can create rules for rewarding desired actions. Every rewarding strategy consists of actions, rules and awards which are the basic game mechanics of the platform in order to create a complete flow.

Action is every task that is already part of the daily workflow of a worker and has a clear beginning and a clear ending. It is the step during a procedure that needs to be completed in order to fulfil a job. The personalized rewarding system supports these actions by attaching awards on them and motivating workers to perform the actions in order to gain them.

Rules connect actions with awards in order to clarify the purpose of the game. The most important thing in rules is that they are adaptable in order to be easy for the administrator to modify them according to risen needs.

Awards are the target in the personalized rewarding concept and they are either scalar awards or badges. Scalar awards are points and usually given when actions are fulfilled based on the rule while badges are exchanged for a predefined amount of scalar awards that the player has already gained.

Additionally, the engine supports the creation of teams in which players are invited to participate and play in multiplayer level. Apart from that, there is the ability to create levels in a rewarding process which are gained by reaching a threshold point of each one as well as achieve quests that are actions available for a specific time interval and offer rewards only if fulfilled in this specified interval. Every team and rewarding strategy has a leader board with the players participating, so that workers can have an overview of the performance of their colleagues. Therefore, an evaluation of the success of the rewarding system is achieved by the performance of all workers which is presented in the leaderboards.

The system is composed of a total of data acquired by mobile applications and questionnaires along with the personalized rewarding engine. These components interact with each other, as the formers inform the rewarding engine about the actions triggered, and retrieve status information which is visualized in the worker's mobile and website interface. The conceptual view of the system, which is an overall monitoring rewarding system, is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual view of the personalized rewarding system

The personalized rewarding system is implemented through an API called GameLayer which store data in their own database so that exploitation of information stored can be done easily and independently of any other integrated tool.

The main objective of the maintenance of balance amongst WI, JB and HQoL is to enhance social interaction among workers, save time, enhance productivity and physical activity and support communication towards problem solving in order to increase satisfaction. The goal of the rewarding engine is to support game mechanics in these activities of the users in order to motivate workers to exercise, rest, communicate with colleagues and supervisor as well as share their knowledge and work experiences to co-workers. Moreover, personalized rewarding engine aims at empowering activities that are of no interest and enhancing an environment with playful elements in order to lead to as longer engagement as possible.

The Ageing@Work solution provides workers a place to (a) exchange knowledge with their colleagues through discussions, (b) request support for resolving high priority incidents, (c) view and share multimedia content related to tasks and use of equipment. For the implementation of the aforementioned functionalities, various social media technologies have been implemented, such as AR solution for training, multimedia-based news feed, and instant messaging. Furthermore, to improve social interaction among colleagues, groups that allow sharing of activities can be created through the leaderboards.

Certain actions of the Ageing@Work solution have been gamified with the use of the rewarding engine. The actions are chosen from the factors that affect the three main indexes of the project, WI, JB and HQoL. Workers of the pilots can collect points when performing certain actions that are useful for the community or actions related to skills enrichment (e.g. watching training videos). The GameLayer engine provides API calls to web services through which any tool can be connected to the engine and gamify its actions. Team-based gamified tasks are ideal for an industrial work environment, however, competition among different teams should not be encouraged. For example, a game to promote collaboration among workers can be created using the gamification engine, involving a recommended but yet important task that is often neglected at the shop floor. In this game, only one team of workers participate (e.g. employees working in a given shift), which competes to its own result of the previous day. As a result of this approach, there will be no workers with the negative feeling of losing the game. However, before starting the game, the rewarding system examines the factors that constitute WI and if a worker is found with high physical fatigue, he/she is offered the opportunity to change shift. If shift is changed and physical fatigue is decreased, the worker is rewarded positively because he/she restored balance.

Two workflows with regard to the integration of rewarding system into the project’s solution are supported by the system: Management of rewarding tasks, and worker’s participation in rewarding tasks. Rewarding tasks’ management refers to the creation, modification, and deletion of rewarding tasks by the administrator. A supervisor or manager of the industry can be the administrator of the platform. Configuration of rewarding engine by an end user is a main feature as it offers convenient adaptation to changing needs. Figure 3 shows the steps required for creating a new rewarding task by the administrator via the user interface.

Figure 3. Rewarding task creation process

At first, the type of rewarding has to be selected. It can be either individual or team based rewarding. In the second case, all users belonging to the same team, contribute to the collection of points and awards. Optionally, the administrator can set possible levels that can be reached, and define the required points for each level. If this is not the case, all participants are by default on Level 1 which is the automatically created base level so as to motivate implementation of additional levels. Subsequently, supported actions are added. In this particular implementation, actions refer to user actions that can be made through the worker’s behavior in both professional and personal life. The awards of the game are defined next.

Different types of awards are supported such as *scalar* (based on collected points), *set* (based on achievements) or *tangible* awards. The administrator can combine levels, actions, and awards by using the rule engine. Rules are fundamental for a rewarding procedure as they define the behavior that a user must follow in order to achieve the reward. Different types of rules are considered, such as action-based rules, reward-based rules, and rules used for advancing to the next level. A multilingual interface for the end users is available, as the gamification engine offers the ability to select display language during the game creation process by the administrator.

A worker is able to view the available rewarding actions and understand how to collect points based on a brief instructions as well as a popularity metric that shows the percentage of the registered participants that have already joined. Once joined to the project’s technology solutions, his/her rewarding actions can be triggered and are passed as input to the rule engine. The worker can leave the rewarding engine at any time. Workflow when participating in a rewarding task is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Workflow when participating in a rewarding task

A tracking mechanism is implemented for the rewarding platform in order to log actions and keep historical data for extracting useful information about it is being used. Each rewarding action, triggered by the worker is recorded along with the timestamp, the ID of the worker, current score, and the ID of the rewarding action. Furthermore, a sequence of activities performed by the administrator of the platform are recorded as well in order to keep historical data for analysis. Activities like adding or deleting a rewarding task, or changing rules in a rewarding strategy can reveal success or failure in the overall design. Additionally, joining or leaving the rewarding system are also recorded because these actions show engagement to the corresponding activities and success or failure of the rewarding system. All in all, the analysis of these logs offers a rich source of information for improving rules and keeping strong motivation.

A set of rules including the factors that affect the three main indexes of the project's scope, is implemented to reward workers for maintaining balance in professional and personal life. The objective of these rules is to promote physical activity, socialization and benefits of leisure time to elder workers. The list of rewarding actions is presented in Table 3 where the personalized rewarding system combines the factors that constitute the indexes of the elder worker's life with the actions that should be done in order to balance work and personal life. Once a factor is measured outside a normal range, the system suggests the appropriate recommendation and if the worker performs it, the rewarding system gives the corresponding points.

Apart from points, there are further game mechanics like badges and progress bars that present worker's state regarding his/her life balance. Badges are gained based on the total of points earned and progress bars represent the status of the worker's factor based again on the points gathered for the specific factor. For example, if a manager needs 50 points for the badge of the "Proactive Manager", the system checks the total of points gathered based on the action "Change worker's job type" to improve worker's self-efficacy. Moreover, in terms of progress bar, if data for "satisfaction with sleep" show less hours of sleep than the recommended, the progress bar for relaxation becomes empty, the recommendation that is correlated with it is "Adjust Shift" thus, it is recommended. Once the recommendation is performed, 10 points are given and progress bar goes up 20%. Afterwards, if sleep data shows improved sleep status, the progress bar linearly goes up until it reaches 100%, meaning the worker is well-rested.

Apart from the aforementioned game mechanics, the flow of the rewarding system awarding with points the performance of an action that concerns a physical activity is the following:

- Each player is a company employee
- Each player has an account and name id
- Each player is registered within a team, and a team is a company department
- A player sets up daily activity missions: such as 5000 steps, 3 km distance, 30 min active time.
- The engine collects the health data (daily steps, distance, active time) from smart phone and watch
- The engine periodically update game server with up-to-dated health data
- The game server converts the steps, distances, active time to points, then converts to credits
- Player uses credits to exchange Prize:

- ✓ 10 credits for a small prize
- ✓ 50 credits for a medium prize
- ✓ 100 credits for a large prize
- Two Leaderboards based on player's accumulated points:
 - ✓ Team Leaderboard: players ranking within a team
 - ✓ Company Leaderboard: players ranking within a company

Table 3. Rewarding actions for enhancing WI, JB and HQoL of life

Workability factor	Measurable Factor	Recommendation	Reward	Health & Quality of Life Factor	Measurable Factor	Recommendation	Reward
Stress	- MoodZoom - VUM Questionnaire	Take more/longer breaks Adjust shift Work from home Take day off	10 points Every 50 points unlock Calmness level	-Stress	- MoodZoom - VUM Questionnaire	Adherence CBT	10 points Every 50 points unlock Calmness level
Negative Feelings	-keyboardAnalysis Questionnaire	Adherence CBT	10 points Every 100 points the avatar is happier	Satisfaction with sleep (6-8 hours)	Questionnaire Third party	Walking (L-M) Running (M-V) Bicycle (M-V)	Battery as progress bar with
Satisfaction with sleep (6-8 hours)	- From Questionnaire the sleep - getSleepData Aggregated	Adjust shift	10 points Every day the progress bar of relaxation fills up 20% after the adjustment of shift and the improvement of sleep data	Concentration	Questionnaire	Walking (L-M) Running (M-V) Bicycle (M-V)	Concentration progress bar
Concentration	Questionnaire	Take a break Take day off	10 points	Self-efficacy	Questionnaire	Notification to the manager for low self-efficacy of an employee	10 points to the manager for adjusting shifts Every 50 points give badge for

							Proactive Manager
Self-efficacy	Questionnaire	Notification to the manager for changing job type of the employee	10 points to the manager Every 50 points give badge for Proactive Manager	Satisfaction with personal relationships	call_logs -> unique calls / keyboard -> message frequency	Adjust shift Work from home	10 points with GPS tracking
Satisfaction with personal relationships	call_logs -> unique calls / keyboard -> message frequency	Adjust shift Work from home	10 points with GPS tracking	Socialization in private life	call_logs -> unique calls / keyboard -> message frequency	Adjust shift -Work from home	10 points with GPS tracking
-Tiring or painful positions	Sedentary activity	Adherence to physical activity	Master of Athletic Badges	- vibrationsHandTools	Sensors, IOT Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
-High Temperatures	Questionnaire	Drink water	At the end of the day -> 50 points	workingHours	Location from GPS	Adherence Stretching Exercises Breaks at work	10 points
-breathing in vapours	Questionnaire	N/A	N/A	Tempo	Location, timeSpent	N/A	N/A
nutrition	Questionnaire	N/A	N/A	-high temperatures	IoT Sensor Questionnaire	Drink water 12 glasses	At the end of the day -> 50 points
-physical fatigue	Questionnaire	Adherence Stretching Exercises	Master of Stretch Badges	-breathing in vapours	Yes / No	Wear appropriate mask	10 points
Satisfaction with the support from friends	VUM Questionnaire	AVC recommendation for meeting with friends	10 points for every meet up Every 100 points, unlocks a level of sociability	-physical fatigue	Questionnaire QIDS, PHQ	- Adherence Stretching Exercises - Adherence Physical Activity	Master of Stretch Badges

Social support from supervisor	VUM Questionnaire	Notification to the manager for low self-efficacy of an employee	Badge for supportive manager		<i>Satisfaction with the support from friends</i>	VUM Questionnaire Location from Mobile	N/A	N/A
Workability Assessment	Workability Questionnaire	Take a break Adjust Shift	10 points		<i>Job satisfaction</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
					<i>Satisfaction with access to health services</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
Motivation and involvement in work	Questionnaire	Work from home	10 points		<i>-Work-life conflict</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
Cognitive demands	VUM part 3 questionnaire	Take a break Take day off	10 points		<i>Variation of work</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
Conflicts and quarrels	VUM part 3 questionnaire	Adjust Shift	10 points		<i>-Repetitive hands or arm movements</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
					<i>OSH Risk Awareness</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A
					<i>Social Support From Supervisor</i>	VUM Questionnaire	N/A	N/A

3.1.4 Results and Outcomes

This section describes the methodology that was followed and presents the results of the application of rewarding system on the project's solution which will take place at two different industries during pilot phase. Both industries involve a shop floor where assembly lines exist and try to balance daily behavior of the workers between professional and personal life. However, different factors affect the indexes that constitute daily balance in a worker's life and this happens due to variations in context and requirements.

Once the worker opens the mobile application, the game server that stores the information from the rewarding system, gets information about health data that are received from smartwatch and the mobile apps. In Figure 5, is presented the abstract infrastructure of the personalized rewarding system and its integration with the mobile application of the project's solution.

Figure 5. Personalized Rewarding Engine for the Wellness Application of Ageing@Work

The worker starts the mobile application and the rewarding system runs as background process the steps shown in

Figure 6 in order to update the status of the worker, examine the daily missions assigned to him/her, update the personal profile, collect data and examine the available rules for rewards based on the new data, update progress bars, team and company leaderboard.

Figure 6. Software flowchart block diagram

In Figure 7, the user interface of the applied personalized rewarding system is shown which implemented an Android Demo App named “Corporate Wellness” by using the online game server, which demonstrated how to motivate employees to be more physically active and keep health.

Figure 7. User Mobile Interface for motivating employees to keep active – Profile, Daily targets and Leaderboard

For the integration of the personalized rewarding system, apart from the conceptual model and strategy, the GameLayer API was used to support technically the idea. The GameLayer API includes the services of creating a rewarding structure by using the admin API, Figure 8, from which the available services are available. An access account should be created by the GameLayer administrator in order to be able and create players, teams, leaderboards and events. As shown in Figure 8, an event can be monitored by checking its unique id and the id of the player in order to understand if it is completed thus, if points should be awarded.

GameLayer

Events
Track what your players are doing

Completes the specified event for the specified player within the given account

Completes the defined event for the specified player within the given account

AUTHORIZATIONS: `api_key`

PATH PARAMETERS

- `id` (required): string, ID of the event

REQUEST BODY SCHEMA: `application/json`

Event completion details

- `account` (required): string (Accountid), ID of the account for the operation
- `player` (required): string (Playerid), ID of the player for whom to perform the operation
- `count`: integer, Default: `1`, Amount of completions for the event
- `mode`: string (Mode), Default: `"increment"`, Enum: `"set"` | `"increment"`, Mode to use for the trigger.
 - `set`: player count is set to the specified value, setting rewards

Request samples

POST `/events/{id}/complete`

Payload

```
Content type: application/json
{
  "id": "new-event",
  "name": "Step Tracker",
  "player": {
    "id": "player-1",
    "points": 51000,
    "credits": 300,
    "mode": "increment",
    "count": 100
  },
  "account": "gameLayer-test",
  "createdOn": "2020-11-01T12:37:10.527Z"
}
```

Response samples

200 **403**

Content type: application/json

Figure 8. Admin API call services

In terms of the personalized rewarding system, the GameLayer API was integrated because it offers the ability to use game features appropriate for motivation and engagement. The missions are the actions that the players are supposed to do within a specific time-frame. Apart from players, leaderboards and teams, the API gives the opportunity to have achievements, levels and prizes which are redeemed by the amount of points that the gathered from the players. Moreover, more distinct rewards are offered like raffles and mystery boxes which are used in order to increase the gratitude of players when winning these type of rewards. All the rewards regardless of type, are designed based on game mechanics and human psychology concepts as mentioned in the previous sections.

4. Conclusions and Future Plan

In this deliverable, the integrated system of personalized rewarding system has been presented which has jointly taken into account both professional and personal life factors, which are stored in the wVUM, in order to reward positively the behaviors that adjust them with benefit to the worker. In order to motivate the ageing worker into behaviors that could keep them active and productive, we investigated user model's factors that constitute workability (WI) and health quality of life indexes (HQoL) separately for each pilot site. Afterwards, we examined the actions that are positively correlated with the factors that constitute either one of the aforementioned indexes in order to gamify them. Thus, once a gamified action is performed correctly the personalized rewarding system awards the worker with the corresponding points which can be exchanged for either badges, prizes, mystery boxes or raffles. This motivation system has as starting point the reward system of Samsung project partner. It is currently focused on productivity and its personalization depends on the wVUM which stores information about workers' targets, aims and specificities like needs, preferences, skills, behavioral preferences and health characteristics. The personalized rewarding system's integration's evaluation outcomes will be presented after the conduction of the envisaged pilot activities.

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